

On Glucosyl Thioureides. Part-III : Synthesis of 4-Aryl-5-phenylimino-3-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,2,4-thiadiazolines

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Certain 4-aryl-5-phenylimino-3-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,2,4-thiadiazolines have been prepared by the interaction of S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides and S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride. The structures of these products have been established on the basis of chemical transformations, polarimetry and ir spectral analysis.

SYNTHESIS of 4-aryl-5-arylimino-3-mercaptobenzyl-1,2,4-thiadiazolines, involving interaction of S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride and S-benzyl arylisothiocarbamides has been reported earlier¹. In view of the utility of thioglucosides in medicinal chemistry, it appeared interesting to synthesise 1,2,4-thiadiazoline having tetra-O-acetyl glucosyl group involving interaction of this isothiocarbamoyl chloride and S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl-isothiocarbamides. The present paper records this synthesis.

Interaction of S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-*p*-tolyl isothiocarbamide and S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride in cold chloroform medium eliminated hydrogen chloride. After standing for several hours and mixing with petroleum ether, an oily viscous mass was isolated. On trituration with ethanol it was converted into a granular solid, m.p. 205°.

The product was found nondesulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. It charred

when heated with sulphuric acid. On thermal decomposition the odour of phenyl isothiocyanate was quite perceptible. When its ethanolic solution was treated with ethanolic picric acid, it afforded a picrate, m.p. 130°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +4.473^\circ$ (*c* 1.5054 in chloroform)²; ν_{max} 700(C-S), 1585 (N-C=N), 1625 (S-C=N), 1330 (C-N) and 1745 cm^{-1} (C=O, as acetyl group in glucose residue)^{3,4}.

When the product was subjected to reduction with ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide the 1,2,4-thiadiazoline ring opened up to form a new product, m.p. 182°. It was found desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution.

These facts indicated that the product with m.p. 182° was a 2,4-isodithiobiuret and could be represented by any one of the two structures, 1-phenyl-4-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl iso-3-*p*-tolyl-2-thiobiuret (IIIa), or 1-phenyl-4-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl iso-5-*p*-tolyl-2-thiobiuret (IVa). The IVA has been synthesized earlier⁵ having m.p. 95°d.

TABLE 1—INTERACTION OF S-TETRA-O-ACETYL-D-GLUCOPYRANOSYL ARYL ISOTHIOCARBAMIDES (0.01 M) AND S-CHLORO-N-PHENYL ISOTHIOCARBAMOYL CHLORIDE (0.01 M). SOLVENT : CHLOROFORM

No.	S-Tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamide (g)	4-Aryl-5-phenylimino-3-S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,2,4-thiadiazolines (I), m.p. °C, yield (g)	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		$[\alpha]_D^{25}$ (<i>c</i> in CHCl ₃)	Picrate m.p., °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.) N
			N	S			
1.	<i>p</i> -tolyl (4.9)	<i>p</i> -tolyl (Ia), 205 (2)	6.63 (6.67)	10.85 (10.17)	+4.473 (1.5054)	130	8.86 (9.79)
2.	<i>m</i> -tolyl (4.9)	<i>m</i> -tolyl (Ib), 163 (1.5)	6.31 (6.67)	10.56 (10.17)	+1.274 (2.558)	110	11.0 (9.79)
3.	<i>o</i> -tolyl (4.9)	<i>o</i> -tolyl (Ic) 157 (1.0)	6.16 (6.67)	10.48 (10.17)	+3.714 (1.6224)	126	8.92 (9.79)
4.	<i>p</i> -phenyl (9.8)	phenyl (Id) 160 (1.8)	6.84 (6.82)	10.90 (10.41)	+1.536 (1.5276)	120	8.92 (9.95)
5.	<i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl (5.1)	<i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl (Ie) 172 (1.2)	6.15 (6.46)	9.41 (9.85)	-3.163 ^a (0.8584)	116	10.15 (9.56)

^aIn acetone.

Therefore, the product (m.p. 182°) was assigned the structure IIIa.

Therefore, the main product (m.p. 205°) has been assigned the structure 5-phenylimino-4-*p*-tolyl-3-*S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,2,4-thiadiazoline (Ia). This was further supported by the fact that when IIIa was reoxidised with iodine in an ethanolic medium the original product Ia was isolated.

The other *S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides also on reaction with *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride under identical reaction conditions afforded the related 4-aryl-5-phenylimino-3-*S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,2,4-thiadiazolines (Ib–Ie) (Table 1).

The mechanism of formation of I may be represented as

where, R = (a) *p*-tolyl
 (b) *m*-tolyl
 (c) *o*-tolyl
 (d) phenyl
 (e) *p*-Cl-phenyl,
 TAG = tetra-*O* acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl.

Experimental

The required *S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides have been prepared as described earlier⁶. The *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride^{7,8} has been prepared by the interaction of phenyl isothiocyanate and calculated quantity of chlorine.

Synthesis of 4-aryl-5-phenylimino-3-*S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,2,4-thiadiazolines (I): To a well cooled solution of *S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-*p*-tolyl isothiocarbamide in dry chloroform (0.01 *M*, 4.91 g in 15 ml) was added gradually a chloroform solution of *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride (0.01 *M*, 2 ml in 10 ml). The reaction was brisk and exothermic with evolution of hydrogen chloride. After standing for several hours no product separated out, but on mixing with petroleum ether an oily viscous mass was isolated. The mass was converted into a white solid (2 g) by treating it with ethanol (10 ml). It was crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 205°. (Found : C, 55.58; H, 4.80; N, 6.63; S, 10.85. C₂₉H₃₁N₃O₈S₂ requires C, 55.33; H, 4.93; N, 6.67; S, 10.17%).

The other 4-aryl-5-phenylimino-3-*S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1,2,4-thiadiazolines were prepared by the interaction of *S*-chloro-*N*-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride with the corresponding *S*-tetra-*O*-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides (Table 1).

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